

Rice-based intercropping systems for rainfed upland conditions of Chotanagpur plateau

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In the upland area of Chotanagpur region (red lateritic, slopy), upland rice, ragi (minor millet), and pulses are grown in rotation with 1 yr fallow. Intercropping pulses or millets with upland rice could increase the cropping intensity of these areas.

We studied the feasibility of intercropping in red soils (pH 5.4, 0.39% organic C, and CEC 12.3 meg/100 g soil) during 1988 wet season.

Ragi (local), green gram (Sunayana), black gram (T-9), cowpea (Gomati), and red gram (BR65) were sown at 20-, 20-, 45-, 45-, and 75-cm row spacing, respectively, as sole crop and as intercrops.

Kalinga III rice was sown in 2:2 row ratio with ragi, 3:1 and 4:1 with red gram, and 2:1 with other crops.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. N was applied as basal to pulses, at 20 kg N/ha. Rice was fertilized with 60 kg N and ragi with 40 kg N/ha. P and K at 17 kg/ha were applied as basal to all crops.

Rice alone yielded 22 t/ha (see table). In the intercrops, highest rice yield was in rice + red gram. Red gram produced the highest yield among the intercrops. Highest rice equivalent yield was with rice + red gram 4:1 ratio and lowest with rice + cowpea 2:1 ratio. All combinations were efficient, with land equivalency ratios of more than one. Highest return was with rice + red gram. ■

Yield of rice and intercrops in Hazaribag, India, 1988 wet season.

Intercropping system	Yield (t/ha)		Rice equivalent yield (t/ha)	Return (\$/ha)	Land equivalency ratio
	Rice	Intercrop			
Rice + green gram (2:1)	1.2	0.2	1.9	312	1.20
Rice + black gram (2:1)	1.3	0.2	1.9	321	1.27
Rice + red gram (3:1)	1.4	0.4	2.5	418	1.32
Rice + red gram (4:1)	1.6	0.4	2.6	438	1.36
Rice + cowpea (2:1)	0.9	0.3	1.7	289	1.12
rice + ragi (2:2)	1.0	1.1	1.7	291	1.02
Rice alone	2.2		2.2	368	1.00
LSD (0.05)			0.2		

Some transplanted rice-based cropping systems

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We evaluated some rice-based cropping systems involving cereals other than rice, legumes, oilseeds, and potato during 1987-88. The alluvial soil was calcareous, sandy loam with pH 8.1 and 0.28% organic C. All crops received recommended fertilizer except sunflower following potato.

Rice equivalent yield was highest with rice - potato - transplanted winter maize (27.4 t/ha), followed by rice - potato - sunflower (21.8 t/ha) and rice - Indian rape - transplanted Swede rape - green gram (19 t/ha) (see table). Productivity of rice - wheat, the dominant cropping system in northern India, was lowest (8.8 t/ha).

Maximum gross return was \$2,970/ha with rice - potato - transplanted winter maize (more than 3 times the \$953/ha return with rice - wheat).

Fertilizer costs were highest (\$247/ha) in rice - potato - transplanted winter maize and lowest in rice - peas - green gram (\$126/ha). Fertilizer return was highest in rice - potato - sunflower and lowest in rice - wheat.

The difference between returns from fertilizer and total productivity is ascribed to the higher fertilizer requirements of rice - potato - transplanted winter maize than in cropping systems involving legumes and oilseeds. ■

Production and returns from some rice-based cropping systems in Punjab, India, 1987-88.

Cropping system ^a	Total grain yield (t/ha)	Rice equivalent yield (t/ha)	Cost of fertilizer (\$/ha)	Gross returns (\$)	
				Per ha	Per \$ fertilizer
Rice - wheat (4.1) (4.3)	8.4	8.8	163	953	5.85
Rice - winter maize (4.8) (4.7)	9.5	11.4	174	1229	7.06
Rice-peas-green gram (4.9) (1.7) (1.4)	8.0	13.5	126	1462	11.61
Rice - Swede rape - green gram (5.4) (1.4) (1.3)	8.0	14.2	148	1579	10.66
Rice - potato - transplanted winter maize (5.6) (20.5) (6.4)	12.0	27.4	247	2970	12.03
Rice - Indian rape - transplanted Swede rape (4.8) (1.8) (0.8)	9.0	19.0	175	2052	11.73
- green gram (1.6)					
Rice - potato - sunflower (4.9) (21.2) (1.3)	6.2	21.8	162	2362	14.58
Rice - Indian rape - sunflower (5.1) (1.9) (1.4)	8.4	15.0	138	1621	11.75

^a Figures in parentheses are yield (t/ha). In the first three systems, rice PR108 (145 d duration) was used; in the other systems, PRTB (125 d duration) was used. ^b Potato tubers.